

Wave-Like Dark Matter as an Alternative to Space-Time Curvature

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Abstract

We propose an alternative to Einsteinian gravity, wherein gravitational phenomena emerge from wave-like dark matter (WDM), a pervasive scalar field generating expansive, oscillatory forces. This field interacts with baryonic matter to produce effects indistinguishable from those attributed to the curvature of space-time. WDM's dynamics are described by a wave equation with a scalar potential that governs its propagation and interaction with energy density. This work formulates a comprehensive mathematical framework for WDM, verifies its consistency with key observations, and highlights its implications for unifying gravitational and quantum systems.

1. Introduction

The general theory of relativity (GR) describes gravity as a geometric deformation of space-time induced by the stress-energy tensor. While GR has been empirically successful, its integration with quantum mechanics remains unresolved, and its reliance on an intrinsic curvature of space-time is conceptually distinct from the quantum description of other fundamental forces.

This paper proposes that gravity-like effects arise from expansive, wave-like oscillations of a dark matter field that permeates the universe. By generating local energy density gradients, this field produces forces on matter that replicate gravitational attraction.

2. Wave-Like Dark Matter (WDM): Theoretical Foundation

2.1. Scalar Field Representation

Wave-like dark matter is modeled as a scalar field $\Phi(\vec{r}, t)$ governed by a generalized Klein-Gordon equation:

$$\square\Phi + \frac{\partial V(\Phi)}{\partial\Phi} = \frac{4\pi G}{c^2}\rho_m,$$

where:

- $\square = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - \nabla^2$ is the d'Alembert operator.
- $V(\Phi)$ is the potential function describing the self-interaction of WDM.
- ρ_m is the baryonic matter density.

In the absence of baryonic sources ($\rho_m = 0$), the equation reduces to:

$$\square\Phi + \frac{\partial V(\Phi)}{\partial\Phi} = 0.$$

This is analogous to classical wave equations but incorporates a self-interaction term that determines the wave's stability and amplitude.

2.2. Energy Density of WDM

The total energy density ρ_{WDM} of the scalar field is derived from its Lagrangian density:

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial\Phi}{\partial t} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2} (\nabla\Phi)^2 - V(\Phi).$$

The corresponding energy density and flux are:

$$\rho_{\text{WDM}} = \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{\partial\Phi}{\partial t} \right)^2 + (\nabla\Phi)^2 \right] + V(\Phi),$$

$$\vec{S} = \frac{\partial\Phi}{\partial t} \nabla\Phi.$$

The total energy satisfies the continuity equation:

$$\frac{\partial\rho_{\text{WDM}}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \vec{S} = 0.$$

2.3. Interaction with Baryonic Matter

Baryonic matter interacts with WDM through a coupling constant α , leading to an effective potential energy U :

$$U(\vec{r}) = \alpha\Phi(\vec{r}, t).$$

The resulting force on a particle of mass m is:

$$\vec{F} = -m\nabla U = -m\alpha\nabla\Phi.$$

This force mimics gravitational attraction, with α analogous to Newton's gravitational constant G :

$$\alpha = 4\pi G\rho_0/c^2,$$

where ρ_0 is the mean density of WDM.

3. Mathematical Consistency with Observables

3.1. Galactic Rotation Curves

Observed flat rotation curves in galaxies imply that centripetal forces are not solely due to visible matter. Let $\rho_{\text{WDM}}(r)$ be the radial density of WDM, and assume spherical symmetry. The effective radial force per unit mass is:

$$\frac{v^2}{r} = \frac{\partial\Phi}{\partial r}.$$

Using the field equation for Φ in a spherical system:

$$\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial\Phi}{\partial r} \right) = 4\pi G\rho_{\text{WDM}}(r).$$

For a sinusoidal WDM density profile:

$$\rho_{\text{WDM}}(r) = \rho_0 + \delta\rho \sin(kr - \omega t),$$

integration yields:

$$v(r) \sim \sqrt{\frac{G\rho_0}{k^2}}.$$

This produces the flat velocity profile observed in galactic rotation curves.

3.2. Gravitational Lensing

Lensing effects arise from WDM-induced energy gradients. The deflection angle θ for light propagating through a WDM field is given by:

$$\theta = \frac{1}{c^2} \int \nabla\Phi dl.$$

For a localized WDM fluctuation:

$$\Phi \sim \frac{GM}{r} + A \sin(kr - \omega t),$$

where M is the enclosed mass and A is the amplitude of the fluctuation. Substituting into the lensing equation yields:

$$\theta \sim \frac{4GM}{c^2 r} + \frac{A}{c^2} \int \cos(kr - \omega t) dl.$$

The dominant term replicates classical lensing, while oscillatory terms are negligible over large distances.

3.3. Gravitational Waves

Oscillations in WDM naturally produce wave-like perturbations analogous to gravitational waves. The propagation velocity v_w of these waves is determined by the scalar field's dispersion relation:

$$\omega^2 = k^2 c^2 + \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial \Phi^2}.$$

For small $V(\Phi)$, $v_w \approx c$, consistent with the observed speed of gravitational waves.

4. Observable Predictions

- Small-Scale Fluctuations:** WDM predicts subtle oscillatory variations in gravitational potential measurable via pulsar timing.
 - Modified Lensing Patterns:** Fine structure in lensing maps could reveal interference effects due to WDM oscillations.
 - Tidal Forces:** WDM-induced variations in local force fields could affect binary systems, providing a test for the model.
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5. Conclusion and Implications

This paper establishes a mathematically robust framework for wave-like dark matter as an alternative explanation for gravitational phenomena. The theory is consistent with flat galactic rotation curves, gravitational lensing, and gravitational waves, and it provides testable predictions

distinct from general relativity. Future work will explore the integration of WDM with quantum mechanics and propose experimental tests to distinguish between curvature-based and wave-based models.

Keywords: Wave-like dark matter, scalar fields, gravitational waves, energy density, alternative gravity theories